

Synthesis and Characterisation of Aquadicyanonitrosyl(2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazolinechromium(I) : A Mixed Ligand Cyanonitrosyl {CrNO}⁵ Complex

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2-(2'-Pyridyl)imidazoline (PYIM)¹ is a strong chelate molecule ($pK_a=8.54$) containing the α -diimine grouping similar to 2,2'-dipyridyl ($pK_a=4.33$)¹ and 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole ($pK_a=3.44$)¹. The formation constants of 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazoline with some metal ions in solution and the effect of coordination were reported by different workers¹⁻⁴. In a recent communication⁵, we reported the synthesis and characterisation of some mixed-ligand cyanonitrosyl {CrNO}⁵ complexes of chromium(I) with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole and related ligands. As a part of our programme on the mixed-ligand cyanonitrosyl {CrNO}⁵ complexes⁶ of chromium(I), the present communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of such complex of composition [Cr(NO)(CN)₂(PYIM)(H₂O)].

Results and Discussion

The observed molar conductance values ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M solution) in ethanol ($7.2 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and DMF ($9.4 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) show that the complex is a non-electrolyte⁷. The values of magnetic moment (1.76 B.M. at room temperature) and g (1.986) for the powdered compound are consistent with a low-spin {CrNO}⁵ electron configuration of chromium(I)⁸.

The electronic spectrum of the complex displays peaks at 775, 425, 345, 240 and 205 nm assigned to $6e \rightarrow 2b_g$, $6e \rightarrow 7e$, $2b_2 \rightarrow 3b_1$, $5e \rightarrow 2b_g$ and $2b_2 \rightarrow 8e$ respectively, considering an M.O. picture applicable to hexacoordinated mononitrosyl complexes of C_{4v} symmetry⁹.

The strong bands at 1 705 and 2 140 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{NO^+} and ν_{CN} respectively, which are in accordance with the assignment reported elsewhere^{8,10}. 2-(2'-Pyridyl)imidazoline possesses three potential donor sites: imidazoline NH nitrogen, imidazoline ring tertiary nitrogen and pyridine ring nitrogen. The ν_{NH} band ($3\ 300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the free ligand remains unchanged in the spectrum of the complex. This suggests that the NH nitrogen of the imidazoline nucleus is not involved in bonding with Cr. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ band of the imidazoline ring is observed at 1 665 cm^{-1} which is shifted to lower frequency at 1 630 cm^{-1} in the complex. The shift of $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ suggests the bonding of PYIM

through imidazoline tertiary nitrogen atom¹¹. The pyridine ring breathing mode of PYIM is observed at 995 cm^{-1} which is shifted to higher frequency at 1 015 cm^{-1} in the complex, and this has been taken to be the diagnostic of coordinated pyridine ring nitrogen¹². The overall ir study concludes that the ligand behaves as a bidentate in the complex. The occurrence of ν_{OH} at 3 560 and 3 400 cm^{-1} is due to coordinated water, which is further supported¹³ by the weight-loss in T.G.A. at 115° corresponding to the elimination of one molecule of water.

Experimental

Ethylenediamine (Sarabhai Merck), picolinic acid (Wilson), hydroxylammonium chloride (SD's), chromic acid (B.D.H.) and potassium cyanide (M & B Chemical) were used as such. 2-(2'-Pyridyl)imidazoline² and potassium pentacyanonitrosylchromate(I) monohydrate¹⁰ were prepared by the reported methods.

[Cr(NO)(CN)₂(PYIZ)(H₂O)] : To an aqueous solution of K₃[Cr(NO)(CN)₅].H₂O (0.01 mol, 3.5 g; 40 ml), an aqueous acetic solution (10 ml; 1 : 1) of 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazoline (0.01 mol, 1.47 g) was added with shaking. The resulting mixture was heated for 25 min over a hot-plate at 80° and the resulting yellow solid was washed several times with dilute acetic acid and with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over silica gel at room temperature to a constant weight (50%), decomp. temp. > 300° (Found: Cr, 17.12; C, 40.32; H, 3.53; N, 28.21. C₁₀H₁₁N₆O₂Cr calcd. for: Cr, 17.39; C, 40.13; H, 3.67; N, 28.09%).

Chromium was determined as Cr₂O₃ after decomposing the complex by strong heating with alkali followed by dissolving in HNO₃ and precipitating by NH₄OH. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Pye-Unicam SP8-100 spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a Varian E-3 spectrometer. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. Molar conductance in ethanol and dimethylformamide ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions) was measured at room temperature using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. T.G.A. was

carried out on a 1090 Dupont thermal analyser with a heating rate of $10^{\circ} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

The mixed-ligand complex was found to be air-stable, soluble in ethanol, methanol and dimethyl-formamide but insoluble in water. The compound after decomposition with KOH followed by acidifying with CH_3COOH gave pink colour with a few drops of Griess Reagent¹⁴, probably due to the presence of nitrosyl grouping.

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